

THE ROLE OF THE PROBATION SERVICE IN THE EXECUTION OF NON-CUSTODIAL SENTENCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10715798>

By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to radically improve the penal legislation” from January 1, 2019, the Probation Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional departments (departments) was founded.

The main tasks of probation departments are:

effective organization of the activities of internal affairs bodies for the execution of sentences not related to deprivation of liberty, in interaction with other government bodies and organizations, as well as public structures;

effective control over the behavior of persons sentenced to parole and those released on parole before serving their sentences;

comprehensive practical support for social adaptation and employment of supervised persons, as well as minors released from penal institutions, including their vocational training;

determine the risk of re-offending by those under supervision and implement preventive measures to prevent it, study their personality by drawing up a socio-psychological portrait.

Today the Probation Service works in 7 areas. As of January 1, 2024, there are 83,763 people under supervision in probation departments. From this:

- correctional labor – 25,862 people.
- 1967 people were sentenced to suspended sentences
- 8577 people are deprived of certain rights
- restriction of freedom – 17,410 people
- compulsory public works – 149 people.
- 29,798 people were released on parole early[1].

Probation service units have been created in 208 districts of the republic, which indicates the positive effect of working with supervised persons.

From the beginning of the probation service to the present, a number of important works have been carried out by industry employees. As a result of the correct implementation of activities, people who have unknowingly committed a crime and come under probationary supervision adapt to social life, secure their employment, prepare them for a specific profession, and fight crime in their

worldview. Certain results have been achieved in terms of developing an honest attitude towards work.

The widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the activities of the probation service is a necessary element in the fight against recidivism and increases the efficiency of activities.

On February 1, 2020, a centralized electronic probation system was launched, which allows you to track and control supervised persons.

Currently, this centralized electronic system is used by the Center for Criminal Legal Statistics of the Prosecutor General's Office, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Agency for Youth Affairs, the Border Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Uzbekistan. Work is underway to integrate with the Unified Information Center Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic.

In addition, in order to effectively monitor the behavior of persons sentenced to non-custodial sentences, the practice of using electronic surveillance devices (electronic bracelets) for persons sentenced to restriction of liberty is being introduced.

In particular, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2020 No. 128 "On organizational measures to ensure the efficiency of institutions for the execution of sentences associated with deprivation of liberty." Subclause 1 of Art. clause "c" provides for the use of 3,000 electronic bracelets in the practice of the Probation Service.

In order to ensure the implementation of these tasks, electronic bracelets produced on the domestic market are worn and tested on convicts serving sentences of restriction of freedom in the Syrdarya and Namangan regions (3 units) and in correctional institutions in the Jizzakh region (6 units).

In international experience, the activities of the probation service consist of 4 types:

During pre-trial probation (Great Britain, Hungary, Slovakia), the psychology and social background of each criminal are separately studied, and the sentences passed against him by the courts are taken into account. Social and legal assistance is provided to defendants and suspects in order to prevent them from committing new crimes, reduce the consequences of committed criminal offenses, and also study the causes and conditions of their occurrence. Creates an individual (individual) program to provide social and legal assistance to persons under pre-trial probation control. The following suspects are placed

under pre-trial probation control: minors; people with disabilities; Women; 58 years and older, pregnant women with children under 3 years of age; men: 63 years and older, single parents of a child under 3 years old. A report of the findings will be prepared and submitted to the court before the trial begins.

Probationary period in legal proceedings - works with the mental state of the accused during the trial.

Penitentiary probation (test in the penitentiary system) - (USA, Sweden, Latvia) preparation for the release of persons serving sentences in penitentiary institutions. Prison probation includes inmates who have one year left before release. When a prisoner is released, he develops and implements a special program together with the probation officer and the administration of the institution, providing them with social and legal assistance.

Post-penitentiary probation, which consists of social rehabilitation of prisoners released from prison.

Above, we briefly got acquainted with the importance of the probation service and foreign experience, based on this, we can make some suggestions for improving the probation service in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Everyone knows that the probation service was created by presidential decree, and this decree sets out the main tasks of the service and the basis of its organizational and legal structure, but there is no separate legal document on the probation service. For any structure to work effectively, first of all, its legal framework must be ideally developed. Therefore, it is advisable to develop the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Probation". If you look at foreign experience, in Japan in 1950 the Act "Voluntary Probation Inspector"[2] was adopted, in the Russian Federation in 2015 the Law on Probation[3], in the Republic of Moldova in 2008 the Law on Probation[4] was adopted in the Republic of Kazakhstan in 2016 Probation Law[5].

These analyzes show that in our country there is a need to develop the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Probation". The organization of the probation service, its direction of activity, concept, purpose, objectives, principles, types and forms of the probation service, as well as the circle of persons to whom this service applies, and the legal status of persons implementing it must be determined by this law. The main purpose of the law:

- creating conditions for moral correction of convicts and post-penitentiary rehabilitation;
- should be defined as the prevention of repeated crimes by persons released from correctional institutions.

Taking into account foreign experience, the legislation of many countries distinguishes four types of probation:

- 1) pre-trial probation period;
- 2) probationary period in legal proceedings;
- 3) probationary period while serving the sentence;
- 4) post-penitentiary probation, which consists of social rehabilitation of prisoners released from prison.

As a result, from the moment a person commits a crime, it becomes possible to cover it up with actions aimed at moral correction, and this is important for turning a criminal into a law-abiding citizen. Taking this into account, it is appropriate to highlight the types of probation in the legislation of Uzbekistan. However, in our opinion, it would be incorrect to introduce the last type of probation, i.e. post-penitentiary probation, which consists of social rehabilitation of prisoners released from prison. The reason is that it is illogical to have the same tasks and powers in two different organizations. Based on this, issues of control and resocialization in the period from the moment a person commits a crime until the moment he is convicted and serves a sentence should be carried out by the probation service, and the process of resocialization with them after the person has served his sentence should be carried out by rehabilitation centers under the jurisdiction of the authorities.

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